

A Lean Framework for Successful Offshore Facility Maintenance Projects in the Oil and Gas Industry

Benedict Amade^{1*}, Chimezie Henry Achaka²,
Onyinyechi Preciousfaith Erumaka³, Erasmus Ejike Duru⁴, Uzoamaka Gloria Chris-
Ejiogu⁵, Chinonso Eke⁶, Ikechukwu Eze⁷ and Oluchi Ebere Chukwu⁸

¹*Senior Lecturer, Department of Project Management Technology, Federal University of Technology, Owerri, Nigeria.*

²*Senior Engineer, TotalEnergies Nigeria Limited.*

³*Lecturer, Department of Logistics and Transport Technology, Federal University of Technology, Owerri, Nigeria.*

⁴*Lecturer, Department of Entrepreneurship and Innovation, Federal University of Technology, Owerri, Nigeria.*

⁵*Lecturer, Department of Finance and Innovation Technology, Federal University of Technology, FUTU, Nigeria.*

⁶*Lecturer, Department of Entrepreneurship and Innovation, Federal University of Technology, Owerri, Nigeria.*

⁷*Lecturer, Department of Logistics and Supply Chain Management, Federal University of Technology, Owerri, Nigeria.*

⁸*Lecturer, Department of Logistics and Transport Technology, Federal University of Technology, Owerri, Nigeria.*

Abstract

This paper has analysed how lean techniques can be used to enhance maintenance projects in the offshore facilities in the oil and gas industry in Nigeria. This was to give a practical example that can lead to waste reduction, enhance efficiency, and facilitate a better delivery of the project. The research design employed was a qualitative study as well as a purposive and convenience sampling method to identify the respondents out of eleven oil servicing companies in the Niger Delta part of South-South of Nigeria. The data were collected using questionnaires, group discussions, visits to the site and direct observations. Fifteen critical success factors (CSFs) to lean implementation in oil and gas offshore facility maintenance projects were modelled using the interpretative structural modelling (ISM) analytical approach. The outcome revealed that management commitment and application of suitable lean tools were the basis of success. The other critical issues were practices of project management, resource availability, management of change, employee involvement, worker training, and continuous improvement culture. The ISM analysis also indicated that there were high levels of interdependence between these factors, and this implies that they cannot be treated on an individual basis. The paper concludes that projects can be made more competitive and sustainable with the application of lean principles being conducted carefully and continuously. It also emphasizes the importance of increased working together between the industry and government stakeholders to enable adoption. The suggested framework can be of effective advice to practitioners, firms, and policymakers who would like to enhance offshore facility maintenance delivery.

Keywords: *Critical Success Factors; Interpretive Structural Modelling; Lean; Offshore Maintenance; Oil and Gas.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The Nigerian economy gains from oil and gas exploration, production, and sales [1]; [2]. International Oil Companies (IOCs) such as TotalEnergies Nigeria Limited, Nigerian Agip Oil Company (NAOC), Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC) and ExxonMobil Nigeria are examples of Oil and Gas Producing Companies (OGPC), as are indigenous companies such as Belema Oil Producing Limited, Seplat Petroleum Development Company, and the government's Nigerian Petroleum Development Company. The oilfield services industry is the backbone of the oil and gas industry, with various Oilfield Services Company (OSC) supporting Oil and Gas Facility Maintenance Projects (OGFMP). As stated in [3], there exists a significant possibility to improve the mobility of resources within site locations, known as workflow, due to the insufficient support provided by current activity-based scheduling methodologies for work-flow planning, which is attributed to practical and methodological limitations. According to [4], lean manufacturing may be employed to address serious oil and gas industry organisational performance issues, affecting both production and service delivery.

This study developed a lean framework for Nigerian oil and gas offshore facility maintenance projects by conducting a survey, exploratory study, and evaluation of OGFMP activities carried out by various oil and gas professionals.

However, [5];[6] argue turn around maintenance (TAM) process improvement strategies are arbitrary, detached and dispersed, and enhancing specific tasks in schedules with no taking into account the entire process would have no significant impact, indicating the need for systemic change.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Lean is the westernisation of a Japanese concept known under various names over the years, including the Toyota production system (TPS), just in time (JIT), pull manufacturing, total quality management (TQM), and others, all of which incorporate some aspects of lean and vice versa [6]; [7]. According to [7], when [8] proposed the lean model three decades ago, it was viewed as a replacement alternative to traditional manufacturing, but it is now widely regarded as the operational paradigm. The phrase "lean" refers to the concepts of lean thinking, lean manufacturing, lean construction, lean organisation, and lean enterprise [9].

Lean philosophy encourages flexibility in production processes, lowers operational costs, and reduces waste of human and non-human resources, all of which have an impact on any organization's effectiveness, operability, and longevity [10].

[8]; [11] confirmed that mass-producers use specifically trained experts to create and redevelop products made by untrained or semiskilled employees, who use costly single-purpose machines to produce uniform items in large quantities, despite the equipment's high cost and insensitivity to interruption. The mass-producer improved buffers, supplies, workers, and space to ensure smooth production, while users received less expensive goods at the cost of diversity and most employees found their jobs boring and discouraging [8]; [11].

As stated by [12], intelligent manufacturing is rapidly advancing in this era of rapid informatization, and it is emerging as a top priority for driving superior expansion in the production sector. Producers can improve the quality of goods and resource utilisation by implementing technologically efficient scheduling techniques, boosting competition in the market and generating more economic advantages.

2.1. Lean principles

According to [13], The idea of being lean originated primarily on the TPS, that sought at turning out exactly the consumer desired at precisely when they needed it while minimising waste. Lean focusses on achieving it properly the initial time and establishing the proper process [6]; [14]. Waste elimination is critical, as all Procedures and operations that deplete resources while adding no value are monitored and eliminated, with the primary goal of getting to know the process, discovering waste, and eradicating it through each step brings us nearer to offering an item that consumers truly want. [8]; [15]. The theoretical framework of lean adjudicates the theoretical principle of value identification in the form as described [14]; [15]; [13]; [8]; [11].

- i. Value – Specifying exactly the worth from the standpoint of the end user.
- ii. The Value Stream – Identifying explicitly an approach that provides the values of the client desires “the value stream” and remove inherent non-value adding steps.
- iii. Flow – Organizing production in a continuous flow or making the product flow.
- iv. Customer Pull – Not producing something when it is required and make it quickly as need.
- v. Perfection - Achieve perfection through continuous enhancement and timely delivery of items that meet client demands, with no inventory.

Offshore facility maintenance is critical to ensuring the safety, efficiency, and reliability of offshore oil and gas asset operations. According to [16], oil and the production of gas is an expensive activity owing to the use of modern equipment and demand for energy, while the worldwide constant rise in power requests, as well as the relationship of crude oil prices with world events, makes the price volatile. Offshore oil and gas facilities include platforms, pipelines, subsea systems, and ships. Furthermore, oil and gas facilities consist of a network of containers, pipes, controls, vessels, and other infrastructure used to accumulate, analyse, evaluate, keep, or discard of petroleum-based substances, gas, or water

2.2. Nigeria’s petroleum and natural gas industry

The energy industry in Nigeria is projected to be worth more than 3.3 trillion USD as of 2019 [17]. [18], posit that, the oil and gas sector supply chain is broken down into three key areas, namely: upstream, midstream and downstream. [17] averred that, the sector has recently suffered great shocks and distress due to fluctuation in prices, inadequate use of capacity, currency exchange problems, theft of pipelines, price inflation, unreliable government policies, and other imbalance in the country's macroeconomic policy, while inadequate capacity utilisation resulted in adverse business environment for most energy-related firms. [18] further explained the three key areas as follows.

1. Offshore facility maintenance can be performed by the facility's owner or operator, as well as by external contractors or service provider’s field. It is highly regulated and affected by geopolitical factors, however, it can provide substantial returns. It is also known as Exploration and Production (E&P).

2. Midstream: These includes transportation, storage and processing of oil and gas. Transportation can be achieved through different means such as trucking, pipelines, tanker ships etc.
3. Downstream: This area refers to the process of raw materials are filtered and refined into derivative products which can be marketed to users. The downstream also includes the marketing and commercial distribution of these products. Some end products include natural gas, fuel, petrol, diesel oil, kerosene, aviation fuel, oil for heating, LPG, lubricants, and bitumen and a lot more types of petrochemicals [6].

The delivery effectiveness of operations in Nigeria's upstream petroleum and natural gas industry has been a source of concern for industry stakeholders. According to [17], a study according to the Nigerian banking sector, it was revealed that a total of N238 billion in NPLs, with N47.572 billion incurred to the oil and gas industry due to bad loans.

According to [19], all maintenance processes include managerial, administrative and technical actions taken during the life cycle of a product facility with a view to restoring the product's facility in a manner that allows it to conduct its desired function of an oil and gas production facility.

During periods of inactivity, companies perform facility maintenance at predetermined intervals to maximise production efficiency and uptime [20]. They went on to say that these intervals are conservative and based on worst-case scenarios, rather than reflecting actual facility and equipment usage. According to [20], maintenance activities may include mobilisation, demobilisation, inspection and testing, periodic maintenance, and in-storage maintenance, which are carried out both offshore and onshore. Offshore facility maintenance necessitates specialised equipment, personnel, and procedures, as well as adherence to applicable standards and regulations. It is also associated with a difficult and expensive task that necessitates meticulous planning, coordination, and execution, necessitating a strategic approach [16].

2.3. Tools and techniques for lean

In the context of lean manufacturing and production, many lean tools are used to improve production and efficiency by making the most of each resource. According to [21], the influence of lean methodologies on business achievement cannot be overlooked, because lean methods and technologies have made businesses more adaptive and profitable, so many companies are investing in the adoption of lean practices to stay competitive. Although lean methods and tools are relevant to all industry settings, the present challenge in market rivalry is the swift implementation of these tools without proper understanding and evaluation [22].

2.4. Critical success factors for lean systems implementation

Critical success factors (CSFs) for lean adoption, also known as success factors, are critical to ensuring the implementation of lean systems and avoiding failure risks associated with financial, time, and employee losses. The CSFs approach has been deployed widely and used in various research fields to identify key critical factors leading to the success of any programme or technique [23]. Various literature clearly indicates that one critical importance or aim of lean system is the elimination of waste is ongoing and feasible, leading to shorter lead time and increased productivity, quality, and on-time delivery [6]; [23]. Table 1 shows the CSFs and their respective sources.

2.5 Critical success factors for lean systems implementation

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Table 1. Critical success factors.

	Critical success factors for lean	Sources	Symbols
1	Top management lends its backing and dedication to lean	[24]; [25]; [24]; [26]; [27]; [28]; [23]	TP
2	Project management, planning and control	[6]	PM
3	Change Management and Corporate Culture	[6]; [29]; [28]; [23]	CM
4	Skills and expertise required for lean implementation	[6]; [26]; [30]; [28]	SE
5	Human resources, employee involvement and attitude	[6]; [11]; [25]; [26]	HR
6	Effective interaction on all levels	[6]	EC
7	Training and education for lean approach	[6]; [27]; [30]; [29]; [26]; [28]	TE
8	Resources and financial capabilities	[24]; [27]	RF
9	Adoption of appropriate lean tools and techniques	[24]; [26]; [27]; [29]; [28]	AL
10	Business plan and a clear vision	[24]; [27]; [28]	BP
11	Active, strategic and visionary leadership	[25]; [28]; [23]	AS
12	Project selection and prioritization	[6]	PS
13	Project monitoring and evaluation of performance	[6]; [23]	PE
14	External factors and their management	[25]; [23]	EF
15	Adopting the culture of continuous Improvement	[29]	AC

3. METHODOLOGY

The study aims to create a lean structure for successful offshore facility maintenance projects in the Nigerian oil and gas industry through an exploratory study based on lean thinking, which allows for the reduction of waste and wasteful operations inherent in the project delivery process. The study employed case study investigation methods. Understanding the practice and process led to the creation of a questionnaire that integrates the content into perspective for the study of the variables that are successful for lean system adoption, and the CSFs of lean maintenance.

Case studies provide credible representations of reality, giving the reader a sense of presence. According to [31], a case study provides an opportunity to conduct in-depth research on a specific topic and typically entails gathering and analysing qualitative and quantitative data. According to [32], case study research is an empirical investigation of a current occurrence in the real-world setting using various kinds of information.

Where applicable to the study objective, questionnaires were distributed to oil and gas facility maintenance professionals. This is due to the technicality and knowledge base required for data collection from respondents in this study area, whereas the Likert scale would be used in the survey that was administered to evaluate reports provided by participants, as suggested by researchers [33]. The researcher administered the questionnaires using methods that were appropriate for the respondent, such as emailing and handing out hard copies in person. The instrument (questionnaire) was divided into parts with one part designed to address pertinent questions raised in the research question, all of which are intended to meet the research's purpose. Each of the items were assessed on a scale of five.

An initial identification of success factors for implementing lean systems was carried out through a literature review using content analysis. Questionnaire survey of facility maintenance professionals from the oil and gas industry was conducted in a bid to validate initially identified success factor using a convenience sampling technique. The identified critical success factors were

ranked and sorted out for CSF by subjecting them through a focused group based on one-on-one interviews with about twenty-one (21) oil and gas industry professionals with an average of 5 years' experience in offshore facility maintenance projects. This was accomplished via ISM technique based on validated critical success factors, which were subjected to a pair-wise comparison survey of very experienced oil and gas field project professionals with long term lean application experience.

The population for the study was limited to OSC working for four major OGPC in Nigeria, with the study population drawn from workers in the selected OSC working on the OGPC's facility maintenance project. The study's population target consisted of oil and gas professionals with extensive experience in OGFMP in Nigeria's Niger Delta region. A focus group was also organised from the population target. The group provided insights and a thorough comprehension of the phenomena under scrutiny. It enabled the researcher to collect more in-depth information at a lower cost than individual interviews. As a result, the survey's stakeholders include project managers, project engineers, project supervisors, quality engineers, and client representatives with hands-on expertise who can relate their experiences to real-life situations. The study used a purposeful method of sampling for selecting respondents, which is more acceptable because it ensures for sampling respondents or participants who have the necessary knowledge, skill, and competence about the research being conducted.

Performance data for this research were collected from a variety of site reports, surveys, feedback, and observations. A survey was designed and distributed to gather facts about the development of a lean framework. The questionnaire was used to figure out the weights of the specified criteria, their relevant factors via the ISM technique, which involves a pair-wise comparison based on specific sets of rules [34]; [35]. The questionnaire was distributed to targeted groups of individuals with extensive experience in oil and gas facility maintenance and other related tasks in the study area.

According to [36]; [34], the ISM is a technique for identifying correlation among various items defining a problem or issue, and it has the following benefits for research. First, the technique is extremely efficient, with question reductions in the ISM questionnaire of up to 80% possible. Second, participants in an ISM-based study do not need to have extensive knowledge of the technique to respond to relational questions (Pair-wise comparison) in the ISM questionnaire. The ISM technique has eight steps.

4. RESULTS

The study sample included eleven (11) OSC that work for four (4) major OGPC in Nigeria, with a study population drawn from workers in the selected OSC who work on the OGPC's facility maintenance projects. Project managers, project engineers, project supervisors, quality engineers, and client representatives all work in the four major OGPCs. Professionals from the 11 OSC working in the four major OGPC firms and projects filled out self-administered questionnaires.

Structural self-interaction matrix (SSIM)

The matrix shown below establishes the interrelationship amongst the row variable i and the column variable j . A sample of respondents was polled in determining the presence and route of the interrelationship between any two variables. Four symbols namely V, A, O, and X were used in representing various types of relationships that exist amongst the two variables in the study. The symbols used in this context are as follows.

i. V- Indicates a situation where there is a directed relationship from

ii. i to j, but not from j to i. A represent a situation where there is a directed relationship from j to I but not from i to j.

iii. X indicates a reciprocal relationship between i and j, while iv. O indicates an unacceptable relationship between the elements.

The structural self-interaction matrix (SSIM) is created by populating the matrix with the group's responses to each pair-wise relationship amongst each element.

Table 2. Structural self-interactive matrix for critical success factors of lean.

CSFs	A	EF	PE	PS	AS	BP	AL	RF	TE	EC	H	SE	C	P	TP
	C										R		M	M	
1 TP	V	X	V	V	V	V	X	V	V	V	V	V	V	V	X
2 PM	O	O	V	V	V	O	A	V	X	O	O	X	V	X	
3 CM	V	O	X	X	O	V	A	A	O	O	O	X	X		
4 SE	X	O	X	X	O	O	A	O	X	X	O	X			
5 HR	O	O	O	O	V	O	X	O	O	O	X				
6 EC	X	O	X	X	O	O	A	O	O	X					
7 TE	X	O	V	X	V	X	O	A	X						
8 RF	O	O	V	V	O	V	O	X							
9 AL	V	V	V	V	V	V	X								
10 BP	O	O	A	O	O	X									
11 AS	A	A	A	O	X										
12 PS	O	O	X	X											
13 PE	X	A	X												
14 EF	O	X													
15 AC	X														

Table 3. Reachability matrix for critical success factors of lean.

Symbols	A	EF	PE	PS	AS	BP	AL	RF	TE	EC	H	SE	C	P	TP
	C										R		M	M	
1 TP	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
2 PM	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0
3 CM	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0
4 SE	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0
5 HR	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
6 EC	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0
7 TE	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	0
8 RF	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
9 AL	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1
10 BP	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
11 AS	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
12 PS	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	0
13 PE	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0
14 EF	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
15 AC	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	0

The reachability matrix (RM) originates from the structural similarity index matrix (SSIM) via transforming the data in each SSIM entry to binary values of 1s and 0. The aforementioned conversion hinges on the correlation shown in table 3 above. The prepared RM is presented, and the representation of a variable being raised to its own self is represented by 1 is also shown.

Table 4. Rules for transforming SSIM to RM.

(i-j) Entry	(i-j) Relation	(j-i) Relation
V	1	0
A	0	1
X	1	1
O	0	0

Dividing the reachability matrix into different levels

A reachability set for a variable is defined as the set of variables with a value of 1 for each same row as the variable. In the same vein, the set for antecedent variable represents variables with 1 as value in its column. When the element is located at the highest level, the point of intersection of the reachability set and the antecedent set becomes the reachability set itself. Each element at the

highest level that satisfy the specified criterion should be removed from the set of variables. The process should be visited until the other levels have been identified. Table 5 shows the iterations performed for all the levels of all variables obtained during these iterations.

Table 5. Partition level of variables from the first to the seventh iteration.

Symbols	Reachability Set	Antecedent Set	R n A	Level
SE	AC, PE, PS, TE, EC, SE, CM, PM	TP, PM, CM, SE, EC, TE, AL, PS, PE, AC	AC, PE, PS, TE, EC, SE, CM, PM,	I
EC	AC, PE, PS, EC, SE	TP, SE, EC, AL, PS, PE, AC	AC, PE, PS, EC, SE	II
BP	BP, TE	TP, CM, TE, RF, AL, BP, PE	BP, TE	III
AS	AS	TP, PM, HR, TE, AL, AS, PE, EF, AC	AS	IV
PS	PE, PS, TE, EC, SE, CM	TP, PM, CM, SE, EC, TE, RF, AL, PS, PE	PE, PS, TE, EC, SE, CM	V
HR	AL, HR,	TP, HR, AL,	AL, HR	VI
PE	AC, PE, CM	TP, PM, CM, TE, RF, AL, PE, EF, AC	AC, PE, CM	VII
AC	AC, PE, TE,	TP, CM, TE, AL, PE, AC	AC, PE, TE,	VIII
CM	CM	TP, PM, CM, RF, AL,	CM	IX
EF	EF, TP	TP, AL, EF	EF, TP	X
TE	TE, PM	TP, PM, TE, RF	TE, PM	XI
RF	RF	TP, PM, RF	RF	XII
PM	PM	TP, PM, AL	PM	XIII
TP	AL, TP	TP, AL	AL, TP	XIV
AL	AL, TP	TP, AL	AL, TP	XIV

Diagram with significant transitive links

The graphical representation of the elements is divided into levels, and the presence of directed and meaningful connections is depicted using the linkages identified in the reachability matrix. Figure 1 shows the comprehensive interpretative model derived from the investigation.

After removing each indirect links in table 6, the final ISM-based framework for implementing a lean system in an offshore facility maintenance project in the oil and gas industry in Nigeria was achieved. Figure 1 depicts the ISM-based framework for implementing lean systems in an offshore facility maintenance project. It was discovered that 'SE is at the topmost part of the hierarchy, indicating the level of effectiveness of lean systems in the offshore facility maintenance project. It is determined by the other CSFs for lean implementation in offshore facility maintenance projects. TP and AL, also formed the foundation of the ISM hierarchy framework, were discovered to be interconnected. These groups of CSFs for lean implementation had the greatest driving force, implying that they were the two key CSFs of lean that influenced the entire offshore facility maintenance project. Next in the level of CSF for lean was PM, which was discovered to affect other lean CSFs but was affected directly by TP and AL. The next level CSF of lean, RF, was found to be influenced by the previously discussed CSFs of lean, but it also had a direct impact on TE. Setting the framework system proper, EF was discovered to have a direct influence on a number of lean CSFs and was thus controlled by other CSFs as well. They include CM, AC, PE, HR, PS, AS, BP, and EC.

Fig. 1. ISM-based framework for lean system.

The interaction matrix is a matrix-based representation of a directed graph. The visual representation gives a clear and substantial indication of the direct and significant relationships between a given factor and all other elements. Table 6 displays an interaction matrix that depicts the relationship between the variables. The symbol "*" denotes a direct link, whereas the symbol "**" indicates a significant transitive link.

Table 6. Interaction matrix.

	CSFs	TP	P	C	SE	H	EC	TE	RF	AL	BP	AS	PS	PE	EF	A	Dr
			M	M		R										C	p
1	TP	1*	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
2	PM	0	1*	1*	1*	0	0	1*	1*	0	0	0	1*	0	1*	1*	8
3	CM	0	1*	1*	1*	0	0	1*	0	0	0	0	1*	1*	1*	0	7
4	SE	0	1*	1*	1*	0	1*	1*	1*	1*	1*	0	0	0	1*	0	9
5	HR	0	1*	1*	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
6	EC	1*	1*	1*	0	1*	1*	1*	1*	0	0	0	0	0	1*	0	8
7	TE	1*	0	0	0	1*	1*	1*	1*	1*	1*	1*	1*	0	1*	0	10
8	RF	1*	0	0	0	1*	1*	1*	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
9	AL	0	0	0	0	0	0	1*	0	1*	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
10	BP	1*	1*	0	0	1*	1*	0	1*	1*	1*	1*	1*	0	0	1*	10
11	AS	1*	0	0	1*	1*	1*	0	1*	1*	1*	0	0	0	1*	1*	10
12	PS	0	0	0	1*	1*	0	0	0	1*	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
13	PE	1*	1*	1*	1*	1*	0	0	0	1*	0	0	1*	1*	1*	0	9
14	EF	1*	0	1*	1*	1*	0	1*	1*	1*	0	0	1*	1*	1*	0	10
15	AC	1*	1*	0	1*	1*	1*	0	0	1*	1*	0	1*	1*	1*	1*	11
	Dep	9	8	7	8	9	7	8	7	9	5	2	7	4	9	4	

Dep=Dependence Power; Drp= Driving Power

Fig. 2. MICMAC analysis.

From the figure above, the fourth quadrant encompasses independent variables that exhibit great driving power and weak reliance power, including TP, AL, EF, HR, PS and RF. The third quadrant is indicative of a collection of linking factors that possess significant driving force and a high degree of reliance. These variables exhibit a certain degree of instability, whereby any modifications made to them can impact both other variables and themselves. The variables include PM, SE, TE, CM, EC, PE, AC and BP. AS can be categorised as dependent variable with poor driving power and strong dependence power. This variable is the only variable in that quadrant. Similarly, no variable appears to have fell in the autonomous quadrant where the incidence of low driving and dependence power exists.

5. DISCUSSION

In developing a framework for implementing lean system in offshore facility maintenance project in the oil and gas industry in Nigeria, the ISM technique based on validated critical success factors subjected to a pair-wise comparison survey based on specific scale was used in achieving this objective. The graphical representation of the elements is organized into levels, and the presence of directed and meaningful connections is depicted based on the linkages identified in the reachability matrix. Figure 1 illustrates the comprehensive interpretative model derived from the investigation. The final ISM-based framework for implementing lean system in offshore facility maintenance project in the Nigerian oil and gas industry was achieved based on final reachability matrix and, after eliminating the indirect links in table 6. The final ISM-based framework for implementing lean system in offshore facility maintenance project is shown in figure 1.

It was observed that SE was discovered to be at the highest level of the hierarchy, indicating the efficacy of all lean system in offshore facility maintenance project. It is controlled by all the other CSFs for lean implementation in offshore facility maintenance projects. This assertion corroborates with that of [26]; [6]; [28]. [30] opined that, team capability is crucial for the success of a project. Given that the project manager and the project staff are ultimately liable for the success and quality of projects, it is only natural that capable personnel would be hired and educated regularly. for effective delivery of project objectives.

The TP and AL constituted the base of the ISM hierarchy-framework, this were found to be interdependent. The aforementioned CSFs for lean implementation had the topmost driving power which means that they were the two main CSFs of lean that influenced the entire offshore facility maintenance project. According to [6], A sound choice of tools is an essential phase when adopting any philosophy, while soft skills are related to values, administrative concepts, people, and

relationships, which are more probable to be affected by possible departures from the perfect organisational climate for the implementation of lean.

The next level CSF of lean was PM which was found to influence other CSFs of lean but was directly influenced by TP and AL. The RF was the next level CSF of lean which was found to be influenced by the previously discussed CSFs of lean but at the same time it directly affected TP. Setting the framework system proper, EF was found to directly influence a number of CSFs of lean and as such was also controlled by other CSFs too. They include CM, AC, PE, HR, PS, AS, BP and EC.

In the MICMC analysis, the fourth quadrant encompasses independent variables that exhibit great driving power and weak reliance power, including TP, AL, EF, HR, PS and RF. As stated by [6], soft approaches contribute to establishing a suitable atmosphere for implementing hard lean tools, by informing managers, employees, customers, and suppliers about the necessity of changing the production system from a lean standpoint.

The third quadrant is indicative of a collection of linking factors that possess significant driving force and a high degree of reliance. These variables exhibit a certain degree of instability, whereby any modifications made to them can impact both other variables and themselves. The variables include PM, SE, TE, CM, EC, PE, AC and BP. AS can be categorized as dependent variable with weak driving power and strong dependence power. This variable seems to be the only variable in that quadrant. Similarly, no variable appears to have fell in the autonomous quadrant where the incidence of low driving and dependence power exists.

The design of the lean framework for implementing lean system in offshore facility maintenance project was derived from the integration of information obtained through thorough literature review, data analysis, and expert input from the OSC and OGPC firms in the offshore facility maintenance industry. The scope of its application is limited to offshore facility maintenance projects.

The lean framework is intended for utilisation by OSC and OGPC firms and professionals, as well as stakeholders, such as consultants, commercial managers, contractors, and clients, in the Nigerian oil and gas industry. It will be primarily used for generating precise information on oil and gas maintenance activities with the soul aim of ensuring there's lean thinking in every aspect in offshore facility maintenance projects. The utilisation of the framework must adhere to the limitations set by the existing regulatory bodies and government policies.

6. CONCLUSION

The researchers set a lean model of maintaining offshore facilities in the oil and gas sector of Nigeria. The results showed that skills and expertise (SE) turned out to be the most important criterion to successful lean implementation whereas top management support (TP) and using lean tools (AL) became the basis of the framework that has the most significant driving impact. Others like project management, resource availability, change management, and employee commitment activities were found to support other roles in the hierarchy.

The MICMAC analysis also revealed that some of the variables were strong drivers with low dependence (e.g., TP, AL, EF, HR, PS, RF), and the rest of the variables were linking or dependent variables, which demonstrate the dynamic nature of the relationships between the CSFs.

The lean framework thus offers an organized approach to OSCs, OGPCs and other interested parties to incorporate lean thinking in maintenance activities, enhance project effectiveness, minimize waste, and achieve sustainable delivery results.

We recommend that effort directed at the professionals, contractors, oil and gas industry players, subcontractors, and other stakeholders and the company wants to use the framework to deliver facility maintenance projects on time, within budget, with high quality, and with stakeholder satisfaction. The one-of-a-kind framework would assist Nigerian oil and gas industry players in successfully delivering offshore and facility maintenance services, as well as creating a platform for venturing into the international oil and gas business, thereby creating a niche to themselves and Nigeria in general. It is believed that the developed framework will further be beneficial to OSC and OGPC firms as it would enable the firms to manage, measure, and evaluate the gains resulting from the deployment of lean systems and its tools and techniques, ensuring an enormous rise and enhancement of the energy industry in Nigeria.

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